

**SYNTACTIC STRUCTURE AND ROLE OF
PREPOSITIONAL PHRASES IN THE KIKUYU
LANGUAGE**

A THESIS PROPOSAL

In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Master's Degree in Linguistics

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Kikuyu, alternatively known as Gikuyu (Gĩkũyũ / ɣekojo /), is a prominent member of the Bantu language family, one of Africa's major linguistic groups. Bantu languages share notable linguistic features, including a complex gender system. Kikuyu is closely related to languages such as Embu, Kamba/Kĩkamba, and Luhya, and more distantly linked to Swahili, Shona, Zulu, Xhosa, and Chichewa. Spoken by approximately 6 million people, Kikuyu is the language of the largest ethnic group in Kenya, primarily in the region between Nyeri and Nairobi in the Central region. Despite its significance, Kikuyu has received comparatively less attention from linguists when compared to other major Bantu languages (Cable, 2010).

This study meticulously examines the syntactic structure and functional role of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu. The investigation is warranted due to the insufficient documentation of Kikuyu prepositions and prepositional phrases. Kikuyu is a Bantu language within the Kikuyu-Kamba Zone E51 and is categorized under the Niger-Congo language family (Guthrie, 1967). "Syntactic structure" entails the arrangement of words and phrases to create well-formed sentences in a language while "syntactic role" pertains to how words or phrases function in a sentence's structure. It involves understanding their contribution to overall grammatical organization, crucial for analyzing relationships between sentence elements. Before exploring prepositional phrases, it's essential to comprehend a phrase as a unit of words expressing a single concept within a sentence's structure. Phrases are grammatical units, forming constituents within clauses.

The Romanization system used for Kikuyu, based on the Standardized Kikuyu Orthography, incorporates diacritics such as the tilde (~) to denote nasalized vowels. Using tilde in words like *thĩĩnĩ* "inside" signifies nasalization, contributing to the accurate representation of Kikuyu pronunciation in the Latin alphabet (Englebretson & Wa-Ngatho, 2015).

In the Kikuyu language, prepositions serve a crucial function as linguistic tools, enabling precise delineation of an object's spatial orientation or direction from the speaker's perspective. This significance is underscored by the intricate system of locative prepositions and postpositions inherent in Kikuyu, distinguishing this language from English, which lacks a similarly complex locative structure (Kihara, 2017).

The term *thĩinĩ* in the Kikuyu language exemplifies linguistic versatility, akin to numerous other languages, by its capability to operate in dual linguistic roles, functioning both as a preposition and an adjective. In its role as a preposition, *thĩinĩ* is adept at conveying spatial relationships, akin to the English preposition “in”. Simultaneously, when employed as an adjective, it imparts characteristics associated with a specific spatial or locative attribute. This dual functionality underscores the adaptability of *thĩinĩ* within the Kikuyu language, highlighting its ability to seamlessly navigate diverse syntactic roles and contribute to the nuanced richness of Kikuyu semantics.

The ensuing sentence examples, along with the subsequent sentences, have been deliberately constructed by the researcher to illustrate a range of linguistic phenomena within specific contexts. These examples, as well as their descriptions, are entirely original and have been created solely by the researcher. The linguistic versatility is exemplified in the following examples:

- (1) *Awa arutaga wĩra thĩinĩ wa igoti rĩa ciana*
 Father does work inside of court of children
 ‘My father works in a children’s court.’

- (2) *Wendo wa thĩinĩ ũrĩ mũciĩ*
 Love of DEM COP home
 ‘Love within is home.’

So, in this context, *thĩinĩ* functions as a demonstrative pronoun, pointing to the specific place of love, and the phrase emphasizes that love comes from within oneself and creates a sense of home or belonging.

Kikuyu employs locative marking, utilizing prepositions to convey specific spatial relationships. These prepositions play a crucial role in specifying the location or position of objects, actions, or events (Aflaki et al., 2022). The sentences provided exemplify the use of these locative elements:

- (3) *Cai wĩ igũrũ rĩa metha*
 Tea COP top of table
 ‘The tea is on top of the table.’

(4) *Nyũmba icio ciĩ gatagatiĩ ka barabara*

House DEM COP middle of road

‘Those houses are in the middle of the road.’

Kikuyu often constructs complex prepositional phrases that involve multiple prepositions and modifiers. Gitonga and Nandelenga (2022) discusses the structure of PPs in Kigeembe, a related language to Kikuyu. Understanding how these components interact and convey meaning can be a challenging but intriguing aspect of Kikuyu syntax.

(5) *A-thiire mbere ya andũ othe*

3SG-went before of people ADJ

‘He went before all the people.’

(6) *Mũthuri nĩ-agĩrĩire gũ-teithia mũka mawĩra ma riko ta*

Man FOC-suppose INF -help wife duties of kitchen COMP

kũruga na gũthabia indo?

cook CC wash utensils?

‘Is a man supposed to help his wife with kitchen duties like cooking and washing utensils?’

Kikuyu prepositional phrases include verbs with specific tenses and aspects, indicating when and how actions are taking place. The interaction between verb tense and aspect within prepositional phrases is unique. Consider these examples:

(7) *Thĩinĩ wa njiarwa ciake nĩ-kũrĩ igongona rĩa kũhoya kirathimo?*

Inside of lineage POSS FOC-PRES sacrifice of ask blessing

‘In his lineage, do we have a sacrifice asking for blessings?’

The verb *nĩkũrĩ* is used to indicate an action of asking for blessings. The tense and aspect of the verb *kũhoya* show that this action is happening at the moment of speaking.

(8) *Nyũmba icio ciĩ gatagatiĩ ka barabara*

House DEM COP middle of road

‘Those houses are in the middle of the road.’

The verb *ciĩ* indicates the location of the houses in the middle of the road. The tense and aspect of the verb show that this is a statement about the current state.

- (9) *Cai wĩ igũrũ rĩa metha*
 Tea COP top of table
 ‘The tea is on top of the table.’

The Kikuyu prepositional phrases exhibit unique characteristics, especially in possessive constructions, making them an interesting subject of study for linguistic researchers. Kikuyu frequently employs possessive constructions to indicate relationships between objects and their possessors. For example:

- (10) *Thĩinĩ wa njiarwa ciake nĩ-kũrĩ igongona rĩa kũhoya kĩrathimo?*
 Inside of lineage POSS FOC.PRES sacrifice of ask blessing
 ‘In his lineage, do we have a sacrifice asking for blessings?’

This sentence exhibits a possessive construction, where *ciake* “his” indicates possession of *njiarwa* “lineage”, and *riya kũhoya kirathimo* “a sacrifice asking for blessings” represents the possessed object.

Among the many linguistic components that make up Kikuyu's intricate syntactic landscape, the prepositional phrase stands out as a fundamental and crucial element. Modern English grammar recognizes five main types of phrases: noun phrase (NP), verb phrase (VP), adjective phrase (AdjP), adverb phrase (AdvP), and prepositional phrase (PP) (Huddleston & Pullum, 2002). Each of these serves a distinct grammatical function in sentence structure.

A prepositional phrase typically consists of three essential components: the preposition, the object of the preposition, and any modifiers situated between the preposition and the object. Example:

- (11) *Mĩgate ĩ thĩinĩ wa gĩkabu*
 Breads COP inside of basket
 ‘The breads are inside the basket.’

Prepositional phrases play a pivotal role in expressing spatial, temporal, and relational information within sentences. The discussion of word categories and their functions is extensively covered by (Quirk & Greenbaum, 1973) and (Quirk et al., 1985).

At the core of every prepositional phrase lies the preposition itself. A preposition serves as a connecting element, establishing a relationship between two entities within a sentence (Svenonius, 2010). This relationship is represented by the prepositional complement, which encompasses a wide range of linguistic elements, including noun phrases, nominal wh-clauses, or nominal -ing clauses (Baker, 2003). Further classifying prepositional complements, Downing and Locke (2006:536) delineate various types, including Noun Phrases (NP), Noun Phrases (Wh-Clauses), and Noun phrases (-ing-Clauses).

According to Downing and Locke (2006:534), prepositions can be categorized into two primary groups: simple prepositions and complex prepositions. Simple prepositions consist of a single prepositional particle. Complex prepositions, on the other hand, are comprised of multiple words. For example, *gatagatĩ ka* and *na* are complex and simple prepositions respectively in Kikuyu.

(12) *Nyũmba icio ciĩ gatagatĩ ka barabara*
 House DEM COP middle of road
 ‘Those houses are in the middle of the road.’

(13) *Yusuf oka na mbathi*
 NPROP came by bus
 ‘Yusuf came by bus.’

Prepositions within the Kikuyu language exhibit additional manifestations. Adverbs, for instance, adopt the post-position *-inĩ* to form prepositional phrases, exemplified by expressions such as *rũciinĩ*, translating to “in the morning,” or *hwaiinĩ*, connoting “in the evening.” Additionally, the incorporation of a locative enclitic (ENCL) *-inĩ* with nouns serves to convey the notion of location, encompassing meanings such as “in, at, near, by.” For instance, *andũinĩ* “among the people” and *mĩciinĩ* signify “in the homes.”

(14) *A-thiire rŭci-inĩ*
 3SG-went morning-in
 ‘He went in the morning.’

(15) *Ngũku ĩ andũ-inĩ*
 Hen COP people-among
 ‘The hen is among the people.’

1.2 Research Problems

Kikuyu, as an under-documented language, poses a significant challenge in comprehending its grammar and syntax, especially regarding prepositional phrases. While studies by Kihara (2017, 2023), Bergvall (1987), and Mbua (2018) have investigated Kikuyu prepositions, they have only scratched the surface of their complexities, highlighting the need for further research. This gap in comprehensive study impedes language learners, educators, and researchers from fully understanding Kikuyu syntax. The syntactic functions and structure of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu are underexplored, complicating efforts to understand the language fully. This gap hinders the development of comprehensive teaching materials and curricula for Kikuyu learners.

1.3 Research Objectives

Drawing from the background information and the identification of the research problem, this study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- i. Identify the syntactic and morphological criteria distinguishing lexical and functional categories in the Kikuyu language.
- ii. Investigate simple and complex prepositions in Kikuyu and highlight any prepositions with unique features.
- iii. Apply X-bar theory to explain the structure of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu.
- iv. Analyze the syntactic roles of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu sentences and illustrate their constituent structures using X-bar theory.

Through these inquiries, the study aspires to contribute substantive insights into the syntactic subtleties of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu, thereby advancing a more profound comprehension of the language's grammatical complexities.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its examination of the syntactic functions and structure of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language, with benefits categorized into theoretical and practical domains.

The theoretical benefits of the study are:

This study makes a valuable contribution to theoretical linguistics by filling a research gap and offering a comprehensive analysis of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu. By investigating syntactic features unique to Kikuyu it broadens linguistic knowledge and enhances our understanding of language diversity and variation.

Applying established linguistic theory to Kikuyu prepositional phrases, the study examines how these theories can be adapted to languages beyond those they were initially developed for. This process may refine or challenge existing linguistic theories, especially those related to syntax.

Furthermore, the research facilitates comparative linguistic studies, enabling linguists to compare Kikuyu's syntactic structures with those of other languages. This comparative approach provides insights into language universals and typological features, contributing to our understanding of the fundamental principles governing human language.

The practical benefits of the study are:

This research aids in documenting and preserving the syntactic structures of the Kikuyu language. As languages evolve, such studies ensure that valuable linguistic information is retained for future generations, supporting language preservation and documentation efforts.

Understanding the syntactic functions and structure of Kikuyu prepositional phrases can benefit language learners and educators by leading to the development of tailored teaching materials and curricula. This enhances language acquisition, making it more effective and culturally relevant.

The study also improves communication within the Kikuyu-speaking community and between Kikuyu speakers and speakers of other languages. By elucidating how Kikuyu speakers construct meaningful sentences, the research fosters better communication.

Additionally, the study sheds light on the cultural significance of the Kikuyu language. Since language is closely tied to culture, understanding the nuances of Kikuyu syntax provides insights into the worldview, values, and cultural expressions of the Kikuyu people.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study encompasses a comprehensive investigation into the syntactic functions of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language. It will delve into prepositional phrases' intricate structures and roles within Kikuyu sentences. The study will explore the syntactic relationships established by prepositions, their complements, and their governing elements, shedding light on how these elements interact within the language. The research will also apply well-established linguistic theory, including X-bar theory, to analyze and understand prepositional phrases in Kikuyu.

This study addresses the research problem of the limited analysis of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language, aiming to fill this knowledge gap. By conducting a thorough investigation, the research seeks to uncover the specific syntactic structures and functions of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu. The analysis will provide valuable insights into the unique syntactic landscape of Kikuyu, contributing to our understanding of this African language's cultural and linguistic significance.

The research will be guided by a set of research questions, including inquiries into the structure, functions, and syntactic aspects of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu. It will also explore the applicability of linguistic theories, such as X-bar theory and the study of Kikuyu syntax. Ultimately, the study's findings will have educational and practical implications, benefiting language learners, educators, and researchers interested in Kikuyu grammar and syntax. Additionally, it informs the development of tailored language teaching materials and curricula to support Kikuyu language learners.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Previous Studies

Within the domain of linguistic research, numerous studies have extensively examined the syntactic functions of prepositional phrases, elucidating their roles across diverse languages. Littlefield (2005) discusses the challenge prepositions pose for theories of syntax, characterizing them as a complex and contradictory category. Conversely, they are classified as one of the four primary lexical categories and are distinguished from functional categories like determiners (Littlefield, 2005:1). Previous studies will be classified into three major categories: “Syntactic Categories,” “Syntactic Structures of Prepositional Phrases,” and “Syntactic Role of Prepositional Phrases,” which form the core basis of this research in the Kikuyu language.

2.1.1 Syntactic Categories

Syntactic categories refer to the classification of words and phrases based on their syntactic properties and structural roles within sentences. This section will explore previous studies that have investigated the syntactic categories, focusing particularly on their manifestations in the Kikuyu language and other languages related to Kikuyu.

Gachomo (2004) conducted a thorough investigation into Kikuyu morphosyntactic verbal inflection within the framework of the Minimalist Program (Chomsky, 1993). The study focused on analyzing tense, aspect, and mood in Kikuyu, emphasizing the intricate interplay between morphology and syntax in determining sentence structure. Highlighting the highly inflected nature of Kikuyu verbs, the research underscored the importance of morpheme sequencing and movement in syntactic representations for feature-checking, thereby influencing sentence construction. Gachomo's work provided detailed insights into how tense distinctions (past, present, future), aspectual nuances, and mood expressions (through affixation and supra fixation) are systematically encoded in the Kikuyu language, contributing significantly to theoretical linguistics within the Minimalist Program framework.

Bresnan and Mugane (2006) delve into the intricacies of mixed categories in Kikuyu, challenging foundational principles of syntax such as endocentricity and lexical integrity. Their study explores how these mixed categories are not only derived through typical inflectional morphology but also through morphological processes that fundamentally alter the lexical meaning type. They specifically note that Kikuyu verb-verb compounds differ from other verb-

involved compounds by not allowing any argument of the constituents to become part of the compound structure. This research underscores the emergence of holistic properties in linguistic constructions, suggesting a departure from the conventional view that all linguistic properties must solely originate from constituent elements.

Dwiga (2008) conducted a study on empty categories within the synchronic syntax of Gichuka, using the framework of the Government-Binding theory proposed by Chomsky (1981). The study aimed to investigate whether the empty categories proposed by Chomsky are universal properties of grammar or specific to Gichuka. Findings indicated that these empty categories are influenced by language-specific factors such as morphological operations and discourse-related features like stress and focus. The thesis concluded that a morpho-syntactic approach is more suitable for capturing the intricate interaction of morphology, syntax, and discourse in Gichuka, suggesting that Government-Binding theory encounters challenges in accommodating certain morphological processes.

2.1.2 Syntactic Structure of Prepositional Phrases

The syntactic structure refers to the systematic arrangement of words and phrases within sentences, governed by grammatical principles. Analysis of previous studies in this domain involves examining diverse linguistic frameworks and methodologies to elucidate the syntactic structure of prepositional phrase constructions across languages. Gitonga and Nandelenga (2022) investigated the application of Chomsky's Minimalist Program to analyze prepositional phrases in Kiigembe, a Bantu dialect. Their study explored whether Kiigembe's prepositional phrases align with the Minimalist Program's principle of simplicity in syntax, proposing a universal structure for phrases across languages. The research delved into phrase structure, the role of the headword in determining grammatical properties, and the hierarchy and merger operations involved in constructing syntactic structures. While referencing English data, the study aims to reveal the structure and semantic roles of prepositional phrases in Kiigembe within the context of minimalist syntactic principles.

Hoffmann (2007) explores the intricacies of English prepositional phrases through a Construction Grammar approach. The study challenges the conventional object/complement versus adverbial/adjunct classification of prepositional phrases in English (Quirk et al., 1985; Biber et al., 1999). Hoffmann suggests a construction-based account that allows for a precise formalization of various types of prepositional phrases, treating them as constructions with differing degrees of schematicity. The proposed construction-based approach facilitates a nuanced understanding of preposition-specific phenomena, including do-so ellipsis, prepositional

passives, and preposition stranding. The paper provides valuable insights into the structure and classification of English prepositional phrases within the framework of Construction Grammar.

Building on the notion of intransitive prepositions (Klima, 1965), Koskoviku and Vokrii (2021) studied intransitive prepositions in the Albanian language. They employed syntactic and lexical analysis to affirm that these linguistic units, traditionally viewed as bi-categorical or adverbs, are indeed prepositions. Their research contends that intransitive prepositions, characterized by projecting a prepositional phrase (PP) at level X with a [-compl] feature, do not necessitate a semantic and structural complement. Introducing the concept of ergative prepositions, the study proposes that the [-compl] feature is not absolute but relative, suggesting a dual feature structure [-compl, + compl] where prepositions may manifest as intransitive or transitive, paralleling the phenomenon observed in transitive verbs with intransitive use. Overall, the findings contribute to a nuanced understanding of intransitive prepositions in Albanian, challenging conventional classifications within the linguistic framework.

Ilori (2015) conducted a study on prepositions in Igálà, challenging the prevailing consensus in previous studies on Igala grammar. The conventional understanding posits the usage of body parts, place nouns, and specific verbs as prepositions in the language. However, Ilori's study approached from both syntactic and semantic perspectives, disputes this claim. The research argues that items traditionally analyzed as body parts and/or place prepositions in Igálà are, in fact, N1 spatial nouns in an [N1 N2] genitive phrase complement of the preposition in a structural context where the preposition head is phonetically spelled out null in the syntax. Notably, the paper contends that in specific contexts, such as *tú unyí un* 'to his/her house,' the term *tú* represents a lexicalized form of a preposition in Igálà. The study contributes valuable insights into the syntactic and semantic aspects of preposition usage in the Igálà language.

2.1.3 Syntactic Role of Prepositional Phrases

The syntactic functions of prepositional phrases encompass various linguistic roles fulfilled by prepositions across different languages, highlighting their essential role in structuring sentences and constructing meaning. This section integrates findings from multiple studies exploring prepositional phrases' intricate roles within diverse linguistic contexts.

Kihara (2017) partially examines the use and positioning of prepositions in connecting nominal arguments within clause structures in Kikuyu. The study shows that prepositions are crucial for linking nouns or pronouns to other sentence elements, relying on nominal arguments for completeness. The placement of prepositional phrases within clauses can vary, including both initial and final positions. This variability is exemplified by the Kikuyu phrase *hando ha*, meaning “instead of,” functioning analogously to English expressions like “in place of.” The study proves

that the variability in prepositional phrase placement allows for the linguistic expression of contrast or substitution in sentence constructions.

In “The 'rural-urban' mix in the use of prepositions and prepositional phrases by students of literature in Kenyan universities,” Mbithi (2022) explores the linguistic challenges faced by Kenyan university students who use English as the language of instruction but have a multilingual background. Additionally, the study focuses on the use of prepositions and prepositional phrases and highlights the cultural and lexical differences between African languages and English. Consequently, the findings suggest that these differences may present challenges for students in conveying academic concepts clearly when using English. Furthermore, the study sheds light on the cultural and linguistic complexities of university students in Kenya, highlighting the lexical and syntactic aspects of linguistic marginalization in their written research papers.

Dulaj et al. (2023) conducted a study aiming to provide a comparative analysis of specific English and Albanian prepositions, with a particular focus on "in," "on," and "at" in English and their equivalent *në* in Albanian. The research addresses the grammatical differences in the usage of these prepositions, suggesting that English prepositions exhibit clearer defined grammatical uses compared to the more generalized translation observed in Albanian. Findings highlight disparities in the classification of prepositions according to cases, the conversion of prepositions into conjunctions, and the position of prepositions in sentences. The conclusion underscores these grammatical distinctions, attributing them to the case system and internal grammatical rules within the Albanian language, ultimately contributing to a deeper understanding of the linguistic variances between English and Albanian prepositions.

Mmadike (2016) presents a case for the existence of prepositions in the Igbo language, challenging the conventional belief that Igbo has only one lexical preposition, *na*. This study argues that Igbo utilizes additional lexical prepositions such as *tupu* “before”, *màkà* “for”, *bànyere* “about, against”, and *gbasara* “about”, in conjunction with other linguistic mechanisms to express prepositional notions. Similar to *na*, these prepositions function as heads, govern, and case-mark their complements, can be fronted with their complements as wh-phrases, and can also function as sentence fragments with their complements. The paper employs the principles and parameters framework and conducts a series of syntactic constituency tests to demonstrate that these prepositions share a common pattern of distribution and belong to the same syntactic category.

Mathonsi (2012) addresses two main issues in their study on prepositional and adverb phrases in Zulu. Firstly, they aim to refute the claim made by Nkabinde (1993) that there are no prepositions and primary adverbs in the Zulu language. Secondly, the research delves into the lemmatization of the categories 'preposition' and 'adverb' for lexicographical purposes.

Consequently, the study suggests that lexicographers should list affixes as separate entries (e.g., *e-*, *o-*, *ka-*, *nga-*) rather than lemmatizing the phrases they appear in, and should only provide the phrases as illustrative examples. This approach aims to improve the accuracy of lexicographical representation.

In Kovbasko's (2016) study, the author examines the overlap between temporal and locative prepositions and adverbs in present-day English (PDE), employing a corpus-based approach to analyze complements, categorized into Noun Phrases and Alternative Complements. Using Sternina's comparative-parametric method, the research challenges traditional interpretations of complement use, revealing that among 94 one-word prepositions, 49 exhibits overlapping with adverbs, particularly displaying locative and temporal semes. The study underscores the deceptive nature of synchronic syntactic approaches and advocates for a diachronic perspective in analyzing the evolution of lexical units from Old English to Middle English periods.

Nasser (2020) conducted a research study investigating the challenges encountered by first-year Iraqi English as a foreign language (EFL) students in correctly utilizing the preposition "on." The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design. Utilizing pre and post-tests, the research aimed to assess the difficulties faced by students in understanding and using English prepositions, with a specific emphasis on "on." The findings revealed common mistakes and identified underlying causes, emphasizing the necessity for targeted interventions to enhance students' proficiency in navigating the nuanced usage of the preposition "on." This research contributes valuable insights into the cognitive-semantic aspects of preposition usage in the context of English language learning.

The existing research on prepositional phrases has shown a limited focus, often neglecting the intricate structures and functions of the Kikuyu Prepositional phrases. Kihara (2017) offers partial insight into the use and positioning of prepositions in connecting nominal arguments within clause structures in Kikuyu, albeit presented in fragmented paragraphs rather than as a comprehensive study solely focusing on prepositional phrases. The discussion emphasizes the essential role of prepositions in linking nouns or pronouns to other sentence elements, highlighting their reliance on nominal arguments for coherence. Notably, the placement of prepositional phrases within clauses can vary, manifesting in both initial and final positions. This variability is illustrated by the Kikuyu phrase *hando ha*, which signifies “instead of” and operates akin to English expressions like “in place of.”

Prior research on the prepositional phrases in Kikuyu has overlooked the incorporation of the X-bar theory. While Mbithi (2022) addresses the linguistic challenges faced by Kenyan university students with multilingual backgrounds using English as the language of instruction without employing X-bar theory, Gitonga and Nandelenga (2022) exclusively apply Chomsky's

Minimalist Program to analyze prepositional phrases in Kiigembe, a dialect closely related to Kikuyu. The latter study delves into phrase structure, the roles of headwords, and syntactic construction operations within the minimalist framework. However, despite these differing approaches, X-bar theory remains pertinent for analyzing prepositional phrases not only in Kikuyu but also in languages with similar syntactic structures. This theory provides a universal framework to understand the hierarchical organization of phrases, including PPs, offering insights into syntactic universals and variations across languages.

Insufficient data analysis to comprehensively explore Kikuyu prepositional phrases is evident. Kihara (2017) partially examines prepositional usage in connecting nominal arguments within Kikuyu, highlighting their pivotal function in linking elements within clauses. The variability observed in the placement of prepositional phrases, exemplified by instances such as *hando ha* ‘in place of’, facilitates linguistic contrast or substitution within sentences. However, the explanations are fragmented across several paragraphs, lacking a comprehensive overview of the syntactic roles and structures of these prepositional phrases. Nevertheless, these fragmented findings underscore the imperative for further research to thoroughly investigate prepositional phrases in Kikuyu, thereby elucidating their syntactic roles and structural properties.

The research’s novelty encompasses two primary aspects. Firstly, no prior studies have delved into the syntactic structure and role of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language using the X-bar theory. Secondly, the study categorizes simple and complex prepositions in Kikuyu, delineating their functions within the language, an area that has been lacking in prior research. This comprehensive approach furnishes a robust framework for dissecting the structures and functions of prepositional phrases within the language. Through meticulous data collection and analysis techniques, this study aspires to furnish an intricate understanding of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language.

2.2 Syntactic Movement in Kikuyu

Syntactic movement refers to the displacement of words, phrases, or constituents within a sentence from their base position to another position. This displacement is often governed by syntactic rules and can serve various purposes in language, including marking emphasis, conveying specific meanings, or satisfying grammatical constraints.

Kikuyu showcases a rich array of syntactic movement phenomena, encompassing both full and partial movement strategies as well as the phenomenon of *wh*-elements being maintained in situ within a sentence. Full movement involves the displacement of elements from their base position to a different syntactic position within the sentence, often for purposes of focus or

information structure. Partial movement, on the other hand, involves the movement of only a portion of a constituent, leaving behind a remnant in the original position. These movements strategies contribute to the overall flexibility and expressive power of Kikuyu syntax, allowing speakers to convey nuanced meanings and highlight specific information within their discourse.

Additionally, the phenomenon of *wh*-elements remaining in situ refers to cases where question words such as *who*, *what*, *where*, and *when* remain in their original position within the sentence rather than moving to a clause-initial position as in many other languages. Kioko et al. (2012) standardized the lexical forms across Bantu languages spoken in Kenya, thereby establishing a unified orthography.

Examples:

(16) *Nĩ-kĩĩ Wanjikũ ahenirie atĩ maitũ nĩ-akũhoya me-nake?*
 FOC-why Wanjikũ cheat COMP mother FOC-pray with-her
 ‘Why did Wanjikũ cheat me that my mother would pray with her?’

(17) *Wanjikũ ahenirie nĩ-kĩĩ atĩ maitũ nĩ-akũhoya me-nake?*
 Wanjikũ cheat FOC-why COMP mother FOC-pray with-her
 ‘Why did Wanjikũ cheat me that my mother would pray with her?’

In both examples, the prepositional phrase *me-nake* meaning “with him/her” occurs after the verb *ahenirie* “cheat”, suggesting a consistent word order pattern where the prepositional phrase follows the verb in Kikuyu sentences. This analysis helps to understand the syntactic structure and word order tendencies related to prepositional phrases in Kikuyu.

2.3 Prepositions in Kikuyu

Various prepositions are employed to denote different relationships and convey specific meanings within the context of the Kikuyu language. These prepositions include *kũrĩ/harĩ*; *kwĩ/he* indicating direction “to”, *kuuma* representing movement “from,” and *na* serving multiple functions such as association, location, possession, and direction. Compound prepositional phrases like *na hinya* “with strength” and *na marakara* “with anger” combine *na* with nouns to express nuanced concepts of intensity or manner. Similarly, compounds such as *narua* “with speed/quickly” and *na-o* “with them” utilize *na* alongside nouns or pronouns to articulate specific qualities or relationships. Additionally, prepositions like *rĩa* and *wa* “of” independently denote possession or association, while the locative enclitic *-ine* appended to nouns signifies proximity

or location and encompasses the meanings “in, at, near, by.” Each preposition manifests uniquely, contributing to the richness and precision of expression in Kikuyu (Kĩhara, 2017).

(18) *A-gucirie na hinya.*

3SG-pull.PST with strength

‘He pulled with strength.’

(19) *Bari amũkorire na marakara.*

Bari meet.PST with anger

‘Bari met him with anger.’

2.4 Underlying Theory

This research adopts the X-bar theory to explore the syntactic structure and functions of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu. The adoption of X-bar theory over frameworks like Government and Binding Theory (GBT) or Minimalist Program (MP) is deliberate. X-bar theory enables the representation of constituent structures, including agreements and various syntactic features such as word order variations, dependency relations, and syntactic categories defining grammatical classes (See Figure 2.4.1). X-bar theory also accommodates diverse word order variations by specifying how heads and phrases can combine while maintaining syntactic integrity, a feature less emphasized in GBT. Moreover, compared to Minimalist Program’s focus on minimizing syntactic operations, X-bar theory provides a more detailed framework for representing syntactic categories and classes hierarchically, thereby enhancing analysis of phenomena such as the roles of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu syntax. Therefore, the X-bar theory stands out as preferable in analyzing the syntactic structure and role of prepositional phrases in Kikuyu. Its universality allows consistent analysis across languages, while its hierarchical framework simplifies complex syntactic structures. The theory’s ability to account for variation enhances its applicability in diverse contexts and languages, and its predictive power aids both descriptive and theoretical inquiries. X-bar theory’s systematic framework helps uncover underlying principles in Kikuyu syntax, and its simplicity and elegance promote clarity. These qualities make X-bar theory a preferred model for syntactic analysis.

2.4.1. X-bar theory

X-bar theory, a fundamental concept in generative linguistics, has significantly advanced our comprehension of phrase structure in human languages (Kornai & Pullum, 1990). Syntactic theories account for a wide range of linguistic facts (Culicover, 1997). This theory transcends mere analysis of nouns and determiners; it encompasses a broad spectrum of linguistic elements, including verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and prepositional phrases (Chomsky, 1980). Within the X-bar framework, each of these elements can function as the head of a phrase, facilitating the examination of their hierarchical relationships. This analysis elucidates how prepositional phrases, along with other linguistic constituents, contribute to sentence structure and meaning.

Notably, X-bar theory relies on the X-bar schema, wherein every phrase can be construed as an XP, representing the maximal projection (Ball, 2004).

X-bar theory, continuously refined and expanded by linguists to accommodate new empirical data and theoretical insights, remains a resilient and adaptable framework within linguistics, emphasizing its enduring relevance (Haegeman, 2006). Its broad applicability spans diverse domains including language acquisition, computational linguistics, and syntactic typology, highlighting its significance in deciphering the complexities of human language and its technological applications. Within the X-bar framework, delineated by distinct levels such as the head, phrase, and bar levels, the term "X-bar" emerges. At the head level, located at the foundation of the hierarchical structure, resides the core lexical element of the phrase, typically a noun in noun phrases or a determiner in determiner phrases (Muriungi et al., 2014).

The phrase level, situated at the pinnacle of the hierarchy, encapsulates the entire phrase, providing a holistic view of its composition. In contrast, the bar level, found in the intermediate position, houses functional elements within the phrase, encompassing items like prepositions and conjunctions. It's noteworthy that both complements and specifiers are marked within brackets, underscoring their optional presence. Any comprehensive theory concerning natural language must account for the consistent ordering of functional heads observed across various linguistic systems (Oliveira & Quarezemin, 2020).

To elaborate, each phrase adheres to the XP format, representing the maximal projection, which can materialize as either a determiner phrase or a noun phrase. This hierarchical structure is elaborated as XP branching into X', serving as both the head and intermediate projection (Chomsky, 1965). Subsequently, X' is divided into the minimal projection, X, housing the head element, alongside any optional complements or specifiers. By applying this theory to analyze prepositional phrases in Kikuyu, one can deconstruct them into hierarchical structures, identify their components (head, complement, specifier), and elucidate the relationships between these elements.

The hierarchical structure within the framework of X-bar theory is depicted. At the highest tier, XP represents the Maximal Projection, capable of embodying either a Determiner Phrase (DP) or a Noun Phrase (NP) (Chomsky, 1982). The intermediate level, X', functions as the Head/Intermediate Projection, encompassing both the core head element (typically a noun or determiner) and intermediate elements. Positioned at the lowest level, X signifies the Minimal Projection, housing the fundamental head element (e.g., a noun or determiner). Importantly, X_{max} must be the most minimal phrase containing Y (Riemsdijk, 1986). Optional complements and specifiers are represented as lower branches beneath X, their presence contingent upon the specific linguistic context (Boumer, 1988). This diagram visually represents the hierarchical arrangement of phrases, culminating in the formation of the Maximal Projection (XP) within X-bar theory.

Figure 2.4.1: The X-bar Theory Structure

Source: (Chomsky, 1993)

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Research Type - A Descriptive-Qualitative Type of Research

As a methodological approach, descriptive-qualitative research seeks to provide a detailed account and understanding of a phenomenon within its natural context, prioritizing depth and complexity over quantification or hypothesis testing (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Creswell & Poth, 2018). In the context of this study on Kikuyu prepositional phrases, the chosen research method aligns with the principles of descriptive qualitative research. Non-probability sampling is employed, where selection is based on the researcher's judgment or specific criteria rather than random selection, facilitating a nuanced examination of Kikuyu prepositional phrases and their significance within the broader context of the Kikuyu language (Patton, 2002, 2015). Therefore, the primary aim of a descriptive study is to portray a phenomenon in its natural context and to elucidate the interrelationships within a given situation (Meyer, 2000). This approach seeks to offer a comprehensive depiction or representation of the Kikuyu prepositional phrases, emphasizing their structures and roles and the connections among the various elements involved.

3.2 Research Site

A “research site” refers to the specific geographical location or setting where a study is conducted to collect data and investigate phenomena of interest. It serves as the physical or virtual environment within which researchers observe, interact with participants, and gather information relevant to their research objectives. The selection of an appropriate research site is crucial as it directly influences the feasibility, relevance, and outcomes of the study (Bickman and Debra, 2009). The research site chosen was Nyeri, Kenya, primarily due to the pervasive use of the Kikuyu language in daily interactions, making it a rich linguistic environment conducive to data collection. Nyeri was deemed suitable for this study because it boasts a substantial population of native Kikuyu speakers who can provide valuable insights into the syntactic structures and roles of prepositional phrases (PPs) in the Kikuyu language. This demographic ensures that the study can effectively investigate these linguistic phenomena within a naturalistic setting, thereby enhancing the authenticity and relevance of the research findings.

3.3 Population and Sampling

The selection of participants for this research involved a meticulous process guided by specific criteria. Twenty individuals were intentionally chosen from distinct age groups: 10 participants aged 20-29 years were chosen to explore potential shifts in the use of prepositional phrases (PPs) and to identify variations in language use compared to the older generation, and 10 participants aged 30-40 years were selected to represent individuals with established linguistic competence and a traditional understanding of syntactic structures involving PPs in Kikuyu. Gender distribution was balanced within each age group, with 5 females and 5 males included in the 20-29 and 30-40 years categories. Males aged 30-40 employed a wider range of vocabulary and sentence patterns in their speech compared to women of the same age group. Additionally, females aged 20-29 used fewer vocabularies and exhibited less diversity in sentence patterns than males in the same age category.

Significant emphasis was placed on selecting participants with a high level of proficiency (selected based on parameters such as language use, vocabulary range, grammatical accuracy, pronunciation and intonation, cultural competence, and comprehension skills) in the Kikuyu language. This criterion ensured that individuals could articulate nuanced expressions, including prepositional phrases, with accuracy and depth. The selection process further prioritized individuals with specific expertise (criteria to gauge expertise in the Kikuyu language was based on level of education, research/publications, teaching experience, and language documentation) in the Kikuyu language, encompassing Kikuyu experts, research experts in Kikuyu, and Kikuyu linguists. This criterion aimed to derive insights from individuals well-versed in the intricacies of Kikuyu linguistic nuances.

In the quest for a more authentic and natural use of language, individuals with notable fluency and oratory skills (based on coherence, clarity, vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and audience engagement) were actively sought. This criterion aimed to capture the dynamic and expressive aspects of prepositional phrase usage. Additionally, participants were selected based on their active willingness to contribute to the research, ensuring cooperative and engaged participation deemed essential for obtaining accurate and meaningful data regarding the usage of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language.

Employing a purposive sampling technique, the data collection process aimed at ensuring a diverse representation of prepositional phrases in different contexts. Consideration of regional variations, dialects, and socio-cultural backgrounds allowed the researcher to capture the richness and complexity of prepositional phrase usage in the Kikuyu language. The combination of written texts and recorded conversations provided a comprehensive examination of prepositional phrases

in both spoken and written forms, contributing to a deeper understanding of their usage within the Kikuyu-speaking community.

3.4 Data Collection

“Data” refers to the factual information collected for analysis and interpretation. This study encompasses qualitative-descriptive. “Data sources” are the origins from which this information is obtained and can be classified as primary or secondary. In this study, “primary data” sources involved original data collected directly through interviews and recordings. In contrast, “secondary data” sources consisted of pre-existing data that have been previously collected and published by other researchers. In this study, the secondary sources included books and articles. The way to collect the data is described in the sub-section below, 3.4.2. Primary data collected from interviews and recordings with native Kikuyu speakers inform the study’s understanding of prepositional phrase (PP) patterns and variations. Comparative analysis with existing Kikuyu language literature validates and contextualizes these findings, ensuring they are grounded in empirical data and aligned with established linguistic rules, accounting for regional and socio-linguistic variations in usage.

3.4.1 Validity and Reliability

“Validity” refers to the extent to which a study accurately measures or reflects the phenomenon it intends to investigate. In this study, several measures were taken to enhance validity. Firstly, structured interviews were carefully designed to address specific research questions related to the use of prepositional phrases (PPs) in Kikuyu language contexts. The questions were tailored to elicit responses that would provide insights into the syntactic structures and patterns of PPs. Additionally, efforts were made to ensure that the interview environment was conducive to open and honest communication, thereby minimizing response bias. Moreover, the manual transcription process using Express Scribe aimed to accurately capture and represent the spoken Kikuyu utterances, maintaining the fidelity of the data for subsequent analysis.

“Reliability” refers to the consistency and reproducibility of research findings. In this study, reliability was ensured through several methodological strategies. Firstly, the use of structured interviews and a systematic approach to data collection helped to standardize the process across all participants. Clear guidelines were established for conducting interviews and recording data using the Zoom recorder, ensuring uniformity in data collection procedures. Secondly, the manual transcription process using Express Scribe involved meticulous attention to detail to minimize transcription errors and ensure the accuracy of the data. Thirdly, the use of X-bar theory for syntactic analysis provided a structured framework for interpreting and comparing patterns of

PPs across different utterances. These measures collectively aimed to enhance the reliability of the study's findings and interpretations.

3.4.2 Research Instruments

“Research instruments” refer to the tools or techniques used by researchers to collect data in a systematic and organized manner to investigate phenomena, test hypotheses, or answer research questions. These instruments are crucial in gathering empirical evidence and generating reliable findings in various fields of study. The research employed various instruments for data collection. To align with the study objectives and to meet the anticipated information requirements, the data collection instruments utilized in this research included interviews, observations, and a Zoom recorder. These methods were deemed most appropriate for the sample population, considering factors such as literacy level, profession, geographical distribution, and cultural background.

3.4.2.1 Interviews

An “interview” typically involves a direct conversation between a researcher and a participant, during which information is transferred to the interviewer (Cresswell, 2012). Interviews are a primary data collection method in qualitative research (Creswell, 2014). Oral interviews constituted another crucial instrument, involving native Kikuyu speakers, language experts, and individuals proficient in Kikuyu. The study involved a total of 20 respondents, divided into two age groups: 20-29 years and 30-40 years. Each group comprised of 5 male and 5 female participants. The research employed structured interviews to gather data on various topics, including the participants’ favorite places in their city, weekend activities, commuting routes, reasons for choosing their current job or field of study, preparation methods for important events or presentations, daily essentials carried in their bags, holiday companions, and comparisons between their current and previous employment experiences.

This approach aimed to capture sentences containing Kikuyu prepositional phrases. This helped to explore the experiences of respondents proficient in speaking Kikuyu, focusing on utterances featuring prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language. By tailoring questions to each participant's background, whether they were fluent Kikuyu speakers aged 30-40 years or learners aged 20-29 years, the research sought to achieve comprehensive data collection and in-depth understanding of their perspectives. This methodological strategy not only facilitated detailed insights into the participants' experiences but also encouraged active engagement, thereby enriching the study’s findings.

The study used this instrument to record the conversations of ten respondents who engaged in discussions about the origins and places of worship for the Kikuyu people. It then gathered the necessary data for analysis, focusing on utterances containing Kikuyu prepositional phrases (PPs). The study also observed how the respondents structured their sentences with PPs to aid in the subsequent syntactic analysis using the X-bar theory. Specifically, the sentences articulated by the respondents were recorded to extract those with prepositional phrases and synthesize them for syntactic analysis. This methodological approach allowed for a detailed examination of the hierarchical structure of phrases, including PPs, within the Kikuyu language, contributing to a deeper understanding of syntactic patterns and constructions.

3.4.2.2 Zoom Recorder

Using a Zoom recorder ensured high-quality audio recording during interviews and conversations, coupled with the proper recording (positioning the microphone correctly, reducing background noise sources) contributed to the overall quality of the dataset. Additionally, the recordings were conducted manually due to the absence of Kikuyu language support in automated transcription tools like Google Translate.

To ensure accurate transcription, the study employed manual transcription software such as Express Scribe. The process involved several steps: firstly, the audio files captured by the Zoom recorder were transferred to a computer. Secondly, using Express Scribe, the researcher listened to each recording carefully and transcribed the spoken Kikuyu utterances into written orthographic text. Special attention was given to accurately capturing the nuances of prepositional phrases (PPs) and other syntactic structures relevant to the study's analysis. This meticulous transcription process was crucial in maintaining fidelity to the original spoken language and in preparing the data for subsequent syntactic analysis using the X-bar theory.

3.5 Data Collection Procedure

The data collection process commenced with a meticulous identification of potential sources of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language. This encompassed various materials, from books and articles to online sources. Additionally, the researcher actively engaged with individuals proficient in the Kikuyu language, including native speakers, language experts, and scholars well-versed in Kikuyu linguistics. The researcher, being a native speaker of Kikuyu, utilized the introspective method to generate some data in this study. This approach involved relying on intuitive knowledge about prepositional phrases (PPs) inherent in the Kikuyu language. The researcher systematically wrote down instances of PPs based on personal understanding and linguistic intuition, subsequently analyzing them for the study's objectives. This method

capitalized on the researcher's native proficiency to access and document linguistic elements that may not be fully captured through external data sources alone.

To ensure a comprehensive and varied collection of prepositional phrases, oral interviews were conducted, and conversations were recorded. This method facilitated the acquisition of authentic, real-life instances of language use across different contexts, such as everyday conversations, formal interviews, and storytelling sessions. Care was taken to conduct interviews with individuals from diverse age groups, educational backgrounds, and socio-cultural settings to create a representative sample. The collected data, comprising both written texts and audio recordings, underwent a meticulous transcription and systematic organization process. Transcription involves converting spoken language into orthographic form while preserving the natural flow and nuances of the original speech. Rigorous review and verification of written texts ensured accuracy, with variations in spelling or punctuation duly noted.

Throughout the data collection process, the researcher maintained detailed documentation for each prepositional phrase, recording its source, context, and any noteworthy characteristics. This information proved essential for subsequent analysis and interpretation, enabling the identification of patterns, trends, and unique features associated with the usage of prepositional phrases in the Kikuyu language.

3.6 Methods of Analyzing Data

The data analysis conducted in this research followed a qualitative approach, specifically employing the three-step technique (Silverman, 2009). This approach was chosen to delve into the Kikuyu prepositional phrases and comprehensively explore their functions and contextual significance.

The first step of the data analysis involved a meticulous review of the collected prepositional phrases. The primary objective of this step was to filter out any entries that were irrelevant or redundant. By carefully scrutinizing the phrases, the researcher aimed to retain only the most pertinent and representative examples for further analysis. The researcher's expertise in the Kikuyu language played a vital role in this step, as it required a nuanced understanding of the language's intricacies, nuances, and subtleties. This understanding enabled the researcher to make informed judgments regarding the relevance and significance of each prepositional phrase.

In the second step of the analysis, the selected prepositional phrases were organized and presented in a tabulated form. This presentation style offered a clear and structured overview of the data, facilitating the identification of patterns, variations, and relationships among the phrases. By visualizing the data in a tabulated format, the researcher enhanced its accessibility and

comprehensibility. This step also allowed for a systematic examination of the data, enabling the researcher to make meaningful comparisons and draw insightful observations.

The final step of the data analysis involved synthesizing the findings derived from the selected prepositional phrases. In this step, the researcher carefully examined the phrases to conclude their syntactic functions, contextual applications, and any noteworthy linguistic features and further analyzed the prepositional phrases using X-bar theory. The analysis adopted a descriptive approach, emphasizing a comprehensive exploration of the inflections and derivations within the Kikuyu language. By delving into the linguistic intricacies of the prepositional phrases, the researcher aimed to deepen the understanding of the language's syntactic structure and usage.

Throughout the data analysis process, the researcher maintained a rigorous and systematic approach to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings. By adhering to a well-defined methodology, the researcher minimized the potential for bias and subjectivity in the analysis. Additionally, any ambiguities or uncertainties that arose during the analysis were addressed through consultation with experts in Kikuyu linguistics. This consultation helped to validate the interpretations and conclusions drawn from the data, ensuring the accuracy of the findings.

3.6.1 Illustrations of Data Analysis

By showcasing select examples of data analysis, this section illuminates how prepositional phrases (PPs) in the Kikuyu language were scrutinized using the X-bar theory. Through detailed exemplars, readers are provided with a comprehensive view of the analytical scheme employed, highlighting the systematic approach used to unravel syntactic patterns and linguistic nuances within the dataset.

- (20) *Cai wĩ igũrũ rĩa metha*
 Tea COP top of table
 ‘The tea is on top of the table.’

Figure 3.5: Kikuyu Prepositional Phrase as a Locative Marker (Example 1)

(21) *Nyũmba icio cĩ gatagatĩ ka barabara.*

House DEM COP middle of road

‘Those houses are in the middle of the road.’

Figure 3.5: Kikuyu Prepositional Phrase as a Locative Marker (Example 2)

In sentence (16) above, the prepositional phrase *igũrũ rĩa metha* “on top of the table” functions as a locative complement. It provides crucial information about the location of the subject *cai* “tea”. The preposition *igũrũ rĩa* establishes a spatial relationship, indicating the place where the tea is located. In this context, the prepositional phrase is essential for specifying the location of the action denoted by the verb “COP” (is). The preposition *igũrũ rĩa* governs the Noun phrase (NP) “table”.

In sentence (17) above, the prepositional phrase *gatagatĩ ka barabara* “in the middle of the road” functions as a locative complement. Similar to the first sentence, this prepositional phrase plays a crucial role in providing specific information about the location of the subject *nyũmba* “houses”. The preposition *ka* establishes a spatial relationship, indicating where the houses are situated. The preposition *ka* governs the noun phrase (NP) *barabara*, specifying the relationship between the governing element and its governed element.

3.7 Research Schedule

TASK	Sep 2023	Oct 2023	Nov 2023	Dec 2023	Jan 2024	Feb 2024	March 2024	April 2024	May 2024	June 2024
Acceptance of proposal										
Proposal initial meetings										
Development of research tools										
Literature Review										
Theoretical Framework										
Research Methods planning										
Data Collection										
Data entry and analysis										
Draw Conclusion										
Draft the project										
Final meeting										

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